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# R code for Marzban et al. (II)
# Disclaimer: This code is not written by a professional coder.

library(terra)          # For reading data
library(ivreg)          # For ivreg()
library(marginaleffects) # For avg_comparisons

my.transf = function(M) # Function for correctly orienting an image in image()
{
temp <- M
  for(i in 1:nrow(M))
    temp[i,] <- M[nrow(M)-i+1,]
return(t(temp))
}

my.rasterize = function(M) # Function for converting a 3d array into a 2d array.
{
tt <- dim(M)
nr <- tt[1]
nc <- tt[2]
nt <- tt[3]
N <- matrix(nrow=nr*nc, ncol = nt)
  for(k in 1:nt)
    N[,k] <- c(M[, ,k])
return(N)
}

treatn <- 401          # Downward shortwave radiation flux
outcomen <- 268        # Surface potential temperature
confn <- c(            # Geopotential height at 29 pressure levels:
  17, 25, 33, 41, 49, # 17=100hPa 25=125hPa 33=150hPa 41=175hPa 49=200hPa
  57, 65, 73, 81, 89, # 57=225hPa 65=250hPa 73=275hPa 81=300hPa 89=350hPa
  97, 105, 113, 121, 129, # 97=400hPa 105=450hPa 113=500hPa 121=550hPa
  129=600hPa
  138, 147, 156, 165, 174, # 138=650hPa 147=700hPa 156=725hPa 165=750hPa
  174=775hPa
  183, 192, 201, 211, 220, # 183=800hPa 192=825hPa 201=850hPa 211=875hPa
  220=900hPa
  229, 238, 247, 256) # 229=925hPa 238=950hPa 247=975hPa 256=1000hPa

confn <- confn[c(3,24)] # Select confounders justified in paper I.
ivn <- c(395,396,397) # Select IVs justified in paper II.

Col <-
colorRampPalette(c("darkblue","blue","darkgreen","green","white","orange","darkorange",
"red","darkred"))(100)

##### read in data and crop #####

grib_data <- terra::rast("../DATA/narrmon-a_221_20010101_0000_000.grb")
colNames <- paste(names(grib_data), as.character(time(grib_data)), sep="_")
Dat <- array(dim = dim(grib_data))
  for(i in 1:418)
    Dat[, ,i] <- matrix(grib_data[, ,i], nrow=dim(grib_data)[1], byrow=T)

exrow_left <- 120          # exclude longitudes/west
exrow_right <- 80         # exclude longitudes/east
excol <- 80                # exclude latitudes

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x0 <- 1 + excol ; xf <- 277 - excol # rows of Dat
y0 <- 1 + exrow_left ; yf <- 349 - exrow_right # cols of Dat
dat_crop <- Dat[x0:xf, y0:yf,]
image(my.transf(dat_crop[, ,outcomen]), col=Col)

dat <- my.rasterize(dat_crop)
dat[,ivn] <- sqrt(dat[,ivn]) # Based on histograms, below.
rm(grib_data, Dat, dat_crop)

##### correlations, histograms, and scatterplots #####

treat <- dat[,treatn] # Define variables treat, outcome, conf, iv
outcome <- dat[,outcomen]
conf <- dat[,confn]
iv <- dat[,ivn]

round(cor.test(outcome, treat)$conf.int,3) # 0.745 0.758
round(cor(iv, treat), 2) # -0.48 -0.41 -0.02
round(cor(iv, conf),2) # -0.45 -0.53 -0.19 -0.16 0.32 0.31

CF <- 1 # 1 (X3) or 2 (X24).
IV <- 2 # 1 (low), 2 (mid), or 3 (high) cloud
x11()
par(mfcol=c(4,2), mar=c(4,4,1,1))
hist(treat, breaks=100, xlab="Treatment/Radiation", main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
hist(outcome, breaks=100, xlab="Outcome/Temperature", main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
hist(iv[,IV], breaks=100, xlab="IV/Cloud", main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))
hist(conf[,CF], breaks=100, xlab="Confounder/Height", main="", mgp=c(2,1,0))

plot(treat, outcome, cex=0.5, xlab="Treatment/Radiation",
ylab="Outcome/Temperature", mgp=c(2,1,0))
mtext( round(cor(treat, outcome),2), line=-2, adj=0.05, col=2)
plot(iv[,IV], treat, cex=0.5, xlab="IV/Cloud",
ylab="Treatment/Radiation", mgp=c(2,1,0))
mtext( round(cor(iv[,IV], treat),2), line=-5, adj=0.05, col=2)
plot(iv[,IV], outcome, cex=0.5, xlab="IV/Cloud",
ylab="Outcome/Temperature", mgp=c(2,1,0))
mtext( round(cor(iv[,IV], outcome),2), line=-5, adj=0.05, col=2)
plot(iv[,IV], conf[,CF], cex=0.5, xlab="IV/Potential",
ylab="Confounder/Height300", mgp=c(2,1,0))
mtext( round(cor(iv[,IV], conf[,CF]),2), line=-5, adj=0.05, col=2)

##### Standardize #####
temp <- dat
for(i in 1:418)
temp[,i] <- (dat[,i] - mean(dat[,i], na.rm=T)) /sd(dat[,i], na.rm=T)
dat <- temp

treat <- dat[,treatn] # Re-define variables treat, outcome, conf, iv
outcome <- dat[,outcomen]
conf <- dat[,confn]
iv <- dat[,ivn]

##### Model: Include all confounders, one IV at a time.
#####

CI_diff <- CI_iv <- CI_adj <- matrix(nrow=ncol(iv), ncol=2)
for(i in 1:ncol(iv)){
lm.1 <- lm(outcome ~ treat)

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diff <- summary(lm.1)$coef[2,1] # Simple difference in means
(OLS).
  CI_diff[i,] <- confint(lm.1)[2,]
    lm.1 <- lm(outcome ~ treat * conf)
    tt <- avg_comparisons(lm.1, variables="treat")
      CI_adj[i,] <- c(tt$conf.low, tt$conf.high) # OLS+adj estimate.
      iv.1 <- ivreg(outcome ~ treat | iv[,i])
      CI_iv[i,] <- confint(iv.1)[2,] # IV estimate.
} # end of for over ivs.

CI_iv[3,] <- CI_iv[3,]/30 # Scale to fit on image.

x11()
boxplot(t(CI_diff), boxwex=0.5, ylim=range(0, CI_diff, CI_iv, CI_adj), axes=F,
xlab="IV",
  ylab="ATE Confidence Interval")
axis(1, labels=c("Low_Cloud", "Mid_Cloud", "High_Cloud*"), at=c(1:ncol(iv)),
cex.axis=1)
axis(2, labels = T, cex.axis = .7); box()
boxplot(t(CI_adj), boxwex=0.3, axes=F, add=T,col=2, border=1)
boxplot(t(CI_iv), boxwex=0.1, axes=F, add=T,col=4, border=1)
abline(h=0, lt=2)

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